

EIC User Group Newsletter Sept. 2019

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NEWS

- A new **Election and Nomination Committee** is in place from Sept. 1st, 2019, until Aug. 31st, 2020:
 - ★ P. Newman (Univ. Birmingham; agreed for second term)
 - ★ C. Weiss (JLab; agreed for second term)
 - ★ A. Deshpande (SBU/BNL; first term)
 - ★ Y. Kovchegov (OSU; first term)
 - ★ M. Ruspa (Univ. P.O. and INFN-Torino; first term)
- A new **Conference & Talks Committee** is in place from Sept. 1st, 2019, until Aug. 31st, 2020:
 - ★ R. Seidl (RIKEN; agreed for second term)
 - ★ B. Pasquini (Univ. Pavia and INFN-Pavia; agreed for second term)
 - ★ C. Munoz Camacho (Orsay; agreed for second term)
 - ★ S. Salur (Rutgers; first term)
 - ★ D. Romanov (JLab; first term)
- The outcome of **recent elections** for Chair and Vice Chair of EICUG **Steering Committee** is:
 - ★ B. Surrow confirmed Chair for a second term
 - ★ R. Milner elected Vice Chair, first term

- The **representative of JLab** in the **EICUG Steering Committee** has changed: R. Yoshida has been replaced by R. Ent
- During the last meeting in Paris, the **EICUG** has selected the date and location of the **next meeting**, which will be held in Miami, 3-7 Aug. 2020
- The **next quarterly meeting** will be held on Oct. 24th, 2020

Recent workshops/meetings of interest for EICUG

<http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous>

Upcoming workshops/meetings of interest for EICUG

<http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming>